

Downscaling ESA CCI soil moisture products: A Comparative analysis of Machine Learning algorithms over West Africa

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This study bridges the fields of AI and space by demonstrating how AI can enhance Earth observation products, specifically focusing on soil moisture (SM) monitoring in West Africa. This study aims to improve the coarse spatial resolution of ESA CCI SM products through downscaling using machine learning (ML) approaches. Three ML algorithms—Random Forest (RF), LightGBM, and Artificial Neural Network (ANN)—were compared for downscaling ESA CCI SM products, utilizing MODIS LST, NDVI, and TVDI data at 1 km resolution as auxiliary variables. Our findings reveal that while all three ML models enhance the downscaling process, the ANN demonstrates the lowest root mean square error (RMSE), making it particularly effective in reducing overall prediction error. However, RF and LightGBM exhibit lower bias, suggesting they provide more consistent predictions across varying SM levels. This comprehensive comparison highlights that the choice of model depends on the specific application requirements—whether minimizing overall error or reducing systematic bias. The enhanced SM monitoring achieved through these methods contributes to better water resource management and climate resilience in the region, supporting sustainable development efforts.

1 Introduction

Soil moisture (SM) is crucial for water and carbon cycles, significantly affecting ecosystem resilience to extreme climate events and sustainable water resource management [1]. However, traditional ground-based SM measurements lack spatiotemporal continuity [2]. Monitoring SM through Earth Observation (EO) is essential for environmental monitoring and resource management. The European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI) provides critical long-term climate data records, including SM products, which are vital for climate research [3]. Yet, the coarse

spatial resolution of these products limits their regional application, especially in West Africa, where high-resolution data are needed to assess climate impacts and support adaptation efforts [4]. To overcome this limitation, downscaling techniques have been developed to enhance the spatial resolution of EO SM products [5, 6].

Various empirical methods and physically based models have been proposed for SM estimation in West Africa [7–9], but they have limitations [10, 11]. Machine learning (ML) approaches such as gradient boosting machine, support vector machine, random forest (RF), and artificial neural network (ANN) have recently emerged as promising alternatives for downscaling EO products, capable of capturing complex spatial patterns and relationships in the data [12–15].

Therefore, this study focuses on comparing and analyzing different ML algorithms for downscaling ESA CCI SM products over West Africa. Accurate SM data are crucial for agricultural productivity, water resource management, and disaster preparedness in this climate-vulnerable region. By conducting a comparative analysis of ML algorithms, including RF, Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM), and ANN, we aim to identify the most effective approach for downscaling ESA CCI SM products to a 1 km resolution, thereby improving data utility for regional applications.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Study area

The study area, West Africa, is a region defined by diverse climatic zones ranging from hot desert conditions in the north to tropical forest climates in the south. Spanning from Senegal in the west to Chad in the east, the area (3°N 26°W; 28°N 26°E) is sig-

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nificantly influenced by the West African Monsoon, resulting in a pronounced north-south gradient of annual precipitation. This gradient is reflected in the varying levels of vegetation cover, with biomass increasing from the arid northern regions to the lush southern areas. The complex interplay of climatic factors and vegetation dynamics makes West Africa an ideal focal point for studying SM patterns.

2.2 ESA CCI

ESA CCI SM products are derived from a comprehensive assimilation process of SM observations collected by both active and passive microwave satellite sensors [3]. Each category utilizes specific algorithms tailored to the characteristics of the sensor data. These products provide daily global coverage with a spatial resolution of approximately 0.25°, equivalent to around 25 km. For the purposes of this research, the combined soil moisture data (version 8.0) for the year 2016 were obtained from the ESA data archive, and they are expressed in volumetric units (m³/m³) [16–18].

2.3 Auxiliary data

The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) data serves as crucial auxiliary data for downscaling coarse-resolution remotely sensed SM due to its fine spatial resolution, extensive temporal coverage, and availability from multiple satellite missions [19]. The MODIS dataset offers valuable information on vegetation indices and Land Surface Temperature (LST). The daily MODIS/Terra LST product (MOD11A1/061) is provided on a global 1 km grid, offering detailed insights into surface temperature variations [20]. The LST data is important because temperature variations directly influence SM dynamics through evaporation and soil thermal properties [21]. Additionally, the daily MODIS/Terra NDVI product (MOD09GA/006/NDVI) was generated from the MODIS/006/MOD09GA surface reflectance composites (Near-IR and Red bands of each scene as $(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red})$), and ranges in value from -1.0 to 1.0 [22]. NDVI is a key vegetation index that reflects vegetation health and cover, which affects SM by influencing water uptake and transpiration. Clouds effects were removed from them, and the Temperature Vegetation Difference Index (TVDI) were calculated using the NDVI and LST data [23, 24]. TVDI integrates temperature and vegetation indices to provide insights into SM conditions, making it a valuable indicator for downscaling. All datasets were uniformly reprojected to UTM zone 30N projection and cropped to the research region. These datasets were selected for their ability to provide complementary information about

factors influencing SM, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the downscaling process.

2.4 In-situ data

The International Soil Moisture Network (ISMN) provides quality-controlled and standardized in-situ SM datasets collected from various operational networks and ground validation campaigns [3, 25]. Available in-situ SM measurements within the ISMN database were gathered [26]. The selected sites in West Africa, covering data for year 2016 were sourced from the African Monsoon Multi-Disciplinary Analysis (AMMA)-Couplage de l'Atmosphère Tropicale et du Cycle Hydrologique (AMMA-CATCH) Network [27], spanning locations in Niger and Benin [28]. ESA CCI SM products represent the top 2–5 cm of soil [3], while optical/thermal RS products capture only the top few millimeters [29]. Therefore, we used in-situ SM measurements at 0–5 cm depth, averaged to estimate daily values, to evaluate the downscale SM results.

2.5 Methods

2.5.1 Machine learning algorithms

In this study, three ML models for downscaling ESA CCI SM products were compared over West Africa: RF, LightGBM and ANN. RF is an ensemble learning method that uses multiple decision trees, combines them to improve prediction accuracy [30]. LightGBM is another ensemble method that uses gradient boosting framework to efficiently handles large datasets by growing trees vertically in a leaf-wise manner [31]. The ANN model used is a feedforward neural network [32], consisting of interconnected layers of neurons, where information flows in one direction from input to output, allowing it to capture complex nonlinear relationships between input features and target variables. Each of these algorithms offers unique advantages in capturing the underlying patterns of SM variability to enhance the resolution of ESA CCI SM products over West Africa.

2.5.2 Downscaling approach

To build the downscaling models, auxiliary datasets were upscaled to match the coarse resolution of the ESA CCI SM products (25 km) using the nearest neighbor interpolation method [33], also, ensuring consistent temporal resolution. A downscaling framework based on machine learning (ML) algorithms was implemented to establish nonlinear relationships between the upscaled input variables and ESA CCI SM values.

In this study, a total of 733,942 pixels were extracted from dataset images over West Africa for the year 2016. These pixels were divided into training, validation, and testing subsets, accounting for 80%, 10%, and 10% of the total pixels, respectively. The training and validation subsets were used to train and fine-tune the model hyperparameters, while the testing subset served as an independent dataset to assess the fit of the final trained models based on RMSE metrics at the coarse resolution.

Finally, the developed models were applied to the auxiliary variables at a 1 km spatial resolution to generate downscaled 1 km ESA CCI SM data for our study area. This facilitated the derivation of high-resolution SM data for further analysis and applications. The in-situ dataset was used to independently validate both the original and downscaled ESA CCI SM products for each model.

2.6 Model Evaluation

To evaluate model performance and the SM downscaling process, four metrics were used: Lin correlation coefficient (CCC), root mean square error (RMSE), R-squared (R^2), and bias.

- **CCC:** Measures the correlation between predicted (\hat{y}) and observed (y) SM values. It ranges from -1 to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating strong positive correlation.

$$CCC = \frac{2\sigma_{xy}}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + (\bar{x} - \bar{y})^2}$$

- **RMSE:** Quantifies the average magnitude of prediction errors. Lower RMSE indicates better performance.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

- **R-squared (R^2):** Indicates the proportion of variance in the observed data that is predictable from the independent variable. Higher R^2 values indicate better model performance.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

- **Bias:** Indicates systematic overestimation (positive bias) or underestimation (negative bias).

$$Bias = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)$$

Where:

- σ_{xy} is the covariance between predicted and observed values.
- σ_x and σ_y are the standard deviations of predicted and observed values.
- \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the means of predicted and observed values.
- N is the number of observations.
- y_i and \hat{y}_i are observed and predicted values for the i -th observation.

3 Results

3.1 Validation of the downscaling ML algorithms

After training the downscaling models, optimal parameters for each algorithm were selected. For RF, the parameters were: `max_depth = 2`, `max_features = 1`, `min_samples_leaf = 1`, `min_samples_split = 2`, `n_estimators = 2`. For LightGBM, the parameters were: `colsample_bytree = 0.924`, `learning_rate = 0.247`, `min_gain_to_split = 0.0010925`, `n_estimators = 50`, `num_leaves = 37`, `subsample = 0.86`. For ANN, the parameters were: `activation = 'relu'`, `batch_size = 64`, `epochs = 50`, `learning_rate = 0.0010`, `units = 64`.

The performance of the ML models is illustrated in Figure 1 – 3. The results show that the training, testing, and validation subsets had similar metrics across all models, indicating effective generalization. The CCC values for all subsets were high, approximately 0.70. Additionally, the predicted SM values closely followed the 1:1 line, demonstrating that the models effectively learned the relationships between the input features and the target ESACCI SM at coarse resolution.

3.2 Evaluation of the ESACCI soil moisture products

To assess the performance of the downscaling ML algorithms in comparison to the original ESA CCI SM data, a validation process was conducted. The SM products, both original and downscaled ESA CCI SM, underwent filtering to include only days present in both time-series for evaluation. Across all downscaled ESA CCI SM variants, a consistently higher correlation (CCC) with in situ SM was observed compared to the original ESA CCI data Table 1. Notably, the ESA CCI SM downscaled using ANN exhibited the highest

Figure 1: Density scatterplot of the ANN model-predicted SM values vs. the target ESACCI SM values.

Figure 3: Density scatterplot of the RF model-predicted SM values vs. the target ESACCI SM values.

Figure 2: Density scatterplot of the LGB model-predicted SM values vs. the target ESACCI SM values.

SM products	CCC	Bias	RMSE
Original SM	0.34	0.08	0.09
ANN-Predicted SM	0.39	0.04	0.05
LightGBM-Predicted SM	0.38	0.03	0.07
RF-Predicted SM	0.38	0.03	0.07

Table 1: Comparative statistics for the in situ validation of the original ESA CCI and downsampled ESA CCI soil moisture by the ML-algorithms. The analysis was conducted for all the sites combined. The RMSE is in m³/m³.

correlation (CCC). Furthermore, the downsampled ESA CCI SM showed reduced bias, with both LightGBM and RF predictions demonstrating similar and the lowest mean bias. The ANN-predicted ESA CCI SM exhibited the lowest root mean square error (RMSE), indicating superior predictive accuracy.

4 Discussion

The comparative analysis of the ML algorithms for downscaling ESA CCI SM products over West Africa has revealed several key findings. The study evaluated the performance of three ML models—RF, LightGBM, and ANN—using specific parameter settings optimized for each algorithm. The results of this analysis indicate that all three models successfully generalized from training to validation datasets, achieving

high correlation values ($CCC \approx 0.70$) across all subsets. This indicates robustness in their predictive capabilities, and suggests that the models did not overfit to the training data and could generalize well to unseen data. However, notable differences in performance metrics among the models warrant a closer examination.

The results show that the downscaling models significantly enhanced the correlation of SM products with in-situ measurements compared to the original ESA CCI SM data. This improvement is consistent across all ML models used. This can be attributed to the downscaling approach in which the nearest-neighbor sampling method was used to upscale the high-resolution input datasets to a 25 km resolution. This preprocessing step smoothed the input data range and removed extreme values, which limited the data points and affected the learning ability of the models [13, 14]. When the trained models were applied to finer 1 km resolution datasets, the greater spatial heterogeneity and richer spatial information led to the presence of input values not seen during training, impacting the model outputs.

Despite achieving similar performance metrics at the original resolution where they were trained, the

ANN showed the lowest RMSE among the models in the downscaling process, which was a key factor in its preference. However, a more nuanced evaluation is warranted. The RF and LightGBM models demonstrated smaller bias compared to the ANN, suggesting they may offer a more balanced prediction across different ranges of SM values. Lower bias indicates less systematic error, which could be crucial in applications requiring high precision across diverse conditions. The superior RMSE of the ANN suggests it performs better in terms of overall low error magnitude, but this does not necessarily mean it is always the best choice. The ANN's architecture and learning mechanisms enable it to model complex non-linear relationships through interconnected layers of neurons, which may explain its lower RMSE. However, the RF and LightGBM models, though less flexible in capturing complex non-linearities, provide stability and reduced bias in their predictions. Therefore, while ANN's ability to learn intricate mappings from high-resolution features (such as NDVI, LST, and TVDI) contributes to its strong performance in reducing RMSE, RF and LightGBM's smaller bias indicates they may offer better accuracy in specific scenarios where systematic prediction errors need to be minimized. Therefore, the choice of model depends on the specific requirements of the application. For tasks prioritizing overall error minimization, the ANN may be preferable, while for applications requiring minimized systematic error, RF or LightGBM might be more suitable. Further discussion of these trade-offs can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the model performance in different contexts [34].

Moreover, despite the promising results, this study has several limitations. One key limitation is the reliance on a limited set of high-resolution features for the downscaling process. While these features have demonstrated a good relationship with SM, the inclusion of additional relevant variables could potentially enhance the accuracy and robustness of the downscaling models. Moreover, the study focused solely on ML models, whereas hybrid approaches that combine physical models with ML techniques might further improve the downscaling performance. Continuous evaluation and validation of these models using extensive in-situ data across diverse climatic and geographic regions will be essential to generalize the findings and improve the applicability of downscaled SM products in various practical contexts.

However, the findings of this study have significant practical implications for improving SM monitoring in West Africa. By enhancing the resolution and accuracy of SM data, these downscaled products can better support agricultural management, drought monitoring, and water resource planning. The ANN model,

in particular, offers a promising tool for generating high-resolution SM data with higher accuracy and reliability.

5 Conclusion

This study bridges the fields of AI and space by demonstrating how AI can improve satellite-derived data products such as ESA CCI. The results show that while all evaluated ML models enhance the downscaling of ESA CCI SM products, each model has its strengths. The ANN model stands out due to its superior performance based on RMSE, highlighting its ability to capture complex non-linear relationships and automatically learn intricate feature representations. However, the RF and LightGBM models exhibit lower bias, suggesting they offer a more balanced prediction across different ranges of SM values. This indicates that while the ANN may be preferred for tasks requiring minimization of overall error magnitude, RF and LightGBM may be more suitable in scenarios where reducing systematic prediction errors is crucial. Future work will focus on optimizing these models further, exploring additional high-resolution features, and addressing the trade-offs between RMSE and bias to enhance the downscaling process comprehensively. This continued refinement aims to leverage the strengths of different models and improve the accuracy and reliability of satellite-derived SM data.

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